

Prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* among Pregnant Women in Sokoto North, North-Western Nigeria

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Abstract

Malaria continues to cause significant morbidity and mortality across Africa, despite the intensification of control interventions. Pregnant women are among the vulnerable individuals infected by the malaria parasites causing adverse effects on both mother and fetus, including maternal anemia, fetal loss, premature delivery and delivery of low birth-weight infants, a risk factor for death. This research was aimed at determining the prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* among pregnant women in Sokoto North, Northwestern Nigeria from February, 2020 to May, 2020. Blood samples of 200 pregnant women who came for antenatal care in the Hospital were collected and questionnaires administered. Thin blood film microscopy and rapid diagnostic test (RDT) kits were used to screen for *P. falciparum*. Results revealed 9.50% (19/200) and 1.50% (3/200) prevalence of *P. falciparum* via RDT kit and Microscopy, respectively. Prevalence of *P. falciparum* significantly associated ($p=0.0027$) with age of the pregnant women as pregnant women within the age group of 27-31 years recorded the highest prevalence with 25.0% (6/24). Although women who are in their second trimester (12.10%), multigravidae (9.6%), widowed (100%), engaged in business (14.30%), with history of using Fansida, Chloroquine and Artemether (63.20%), used bed net (84.20%) and without formal education (10.50%) were the highest infected, the occurrence of the parasite does not associate ($p>0.05$) with any of the parameters. This research has revealed high prevalence of *P. falciparum* malaria among pregnant women in the study area. Pregnant women should be going for early ante-natal care booking and attend clinic regularly. Additionally, malaria control programs should be carried out in the study area.

Keywords: Malaria, Rapid Diagnostic Test Kits (RDT), *Plasmodium falciparum*, Pregnant women, Prevalence

1.0 Introduction

Malaria is an infectious disease caused by protozoan parasites from the genus *Plasmodium* that can be transmitted by the bite of the *Anopheles* mosquito with *falciparum* malaria the deadliest type [30]. Symptoms of malaria include cycles of chills, fever, sweats, muscle aches and headache that recur every few day [30]. There can also be vomiting, diarrhea, coughing, and yellowing (jaundice) of the skin and eye [30]. Persons with severe *falciparum* malaria can develop bleeding problems, shock, kidney and liver failure, central nervous system problems, coma, and death [30].

Malaria is caused by *Plasmodium* spp. with most of the infections cause by *Plasmodium falciparum* [17]. *P. falciparum* is a protozoan parasite belonging to phylum Apicomplexa, class Aconoidasida, order Haemosporida, family Plasmodiidae, and genus *Plasmodium* [30]. The success of *P. falciparum* as a parasite has been attributed partly to its enormous genetic diversity that allows it to adapt to anti-malarial and hinder the development of an effective vaccine [24]. Parasite populations respond to specific interventions, such as rapid diagnostic tests, human host immune pressure and mosquito vector environment [18, 12, 27]. Malaria is transmitted to people through the bites of infected female

Anopheles spp. of mosquitoes which inject or inoculate the infective stage (sporozoite) of *Plasmodium* parasite into the blood of the host. Malaria continues to cause significant morbidity and mortality across Africa, despite the intensification of control interventions [30]. A worldwide decline in its burden was reported in 2015, with a rebound and age shift in morbidity as control and interventions are scaled up [25,13,3,1,29]. Reports suggest that malaria incidence increased between 2014 and 2017 in several regions across sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), where most of the global investments in control and elimination are spent [30]. Malaria remains the most prevalent parasitic disease in tropical and subtropical regions of the world [30]. According to a 2016 World Health Organization report, more than 212 million cases of malaria were recorded annually and approximately 429,000 people died from malaria worldwide [29]. In Southeast Asia, 15 million cases (7% global cases) and 26,000 deaths (6% global deaths) are reportedly associated with malaria each year [29]. Research conducted [4] in Sokoto, Nigeria indicated that the prevalence of malaria is higher in pregnant women and suggested the need for the promotion of insecticide-treated bed nets (ITNs) and intermittent preventive treatment (IPTp) to protect pregnant women in the area from malaria. There is the need for interventions such as mass media campaigns peer/outreach education, life skill programs to educate women on the advantages of early antenatal care (ANC) booking and the need to attend clinic regularly [4]. Adults who have survived repeated malaria infections throughout their lifetimes may become partially immune to severe or fatal malaria. However, because of the changes in women's immune systems during pregnancy and the presence of a new organ (the placenta) with new places for parasites to bind, pregnant women lose some of their immunity to malaria infection [5].

Malaria infection during pregnancy can have adverse effects on both mother and fetus, including maternal anemia, fetal loss, premature delivery, intrauterine growth retardation, and delivery of low birth-weight infants (<2500 g or <5.5 pounds), a risk factor for death [5].

Currently, malaria chemotherapy relies mainly on the sustained efficacy of artemisinin-based combination therapy (ACT), which is the recommended drugs, for the treatment of adults and children with uncomplicated *P.*

falciparum infection [28]. The ACT combines artemisinin derivatives and other long-acting anti-malarial, with a different mechanism of action, to maximize the chances of eliminating parasites during treatment, but also to limit the possibility of a spontaneous mutation that will confer resistance to both drugs [24]. Due to adverse effects of malaria infection during pregnancy, an up to date data on malaria cases in relation to associated risk factors is required to access current epidemiology of malaria in pregnant women. While previous researches offer insights into malaria prevalence in pregnant women in general, specific gaps remain regarding *Plasmodium falciparum* in Sokoto North Local Government.

There is lack of robust baseline data on *P. falciparum* prevalence in pregnant women in Sokoto South makes it difficult to track trends and measure the impact of interventions, microscopic vs. rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs): Discrepancies between microscopy and RDT results have been reported in some settings. Studies comparing the accuracy of different diagnostic methods in this specific population are necessary and a deeper understanding of the specific risk factors and determinants of *P. falciparum* infection in pregnant women in Sokoto North is needed. This could include factors like socio-economic status, access to healthcare, and adherence to preventative measures. By addressing these research gaps, we can gain a deeper understanding of the burden of *P. falciparum* malaria in pregnant women in Sokoto North and develop more effective interventions to protect both mothers and their children. Determining the Prevalence of *P. falciparum* among pregnant women will also provide awareness to pharmaceutical companies, the government and the pregnant women to know their status of malaria. It will also form basis for further research.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

Sokoto town is located in the extreme northwest of Nigeria, near the confluence of the Sokoto River and the River Rima. As of 2024, Sokoto have a projected population of 734,255. Sokoto town is the capital of Sokoto State [7].

Sokoto experiences a hot semi-arid climate. It is located in the dry Sahel surrounded by sandy Savannah and isolated hills with an annual

average temperature of 28.3 °C (82.9 °F) and maximum daytime temperatures are generally under 40 °C (104.0 °F) for most of the year. The warmest months are February to April, where daytime temperatures can exceed 45 °C (113.0 °F). The highest recorded temperature is 47.2 °C (117.0 °F), which is also the highest recorded temperature in Nigeria. The rainy season is from June to October [7]. From late October to February is the cold season where the climate is dominated by the harmattan wind blowing Sahara dust over the land [7].

Sokoto State is located in the savannah zone with land area of 28,232.37 sq kilometer. It's located between latitude 11° 30" to 13° 50" North and

longitudes 4° to 6° East. It's bordered in the north by Niger Republic, Zamfara state to the North and Kebbi state to the south and west [7].

Maryam Abacha Women and Children Hospital Sokoto is located along Sultan Bello road Sokoto in Sokoto North LGA, Sokoto, Nigeria. The women and Children health care clinic was constructed in the year 1997, and commissioned by her Excellency the wife of the President, Maryam Sani Abacha. The hospital was commissioned by her to cater for the problem being faced by women and children which include Vesico Vaginal Fistula (VVF). The hospital is conducting surgery for such cases successfully, since its inception [15]

Figure 1: The Study Area.

Source: Department of Geography UDUS, 2021

2.2 Ethical approval and consent to participate

Prior to the commencement of the research work, ethical approval was obtained from the research and ethical committee of Maryam Abacha women and children hospital (MAWCH) Sokoto State, Nigeria. Blood samples were collected from consenting patients who were clearly informed on the aim and objectives of the research. Introduction letter was obtained from the Head of Biological Sciences department, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, which was addressed to the management of MAWCH seeking them to assist and give access to their facilities.

Open ended/closed ended questionnaire was also distributed to participating pregnant women.

2.3 Sample size determination

Sample size for the study was calculated using the formula: $n = Z^2 p (1-P) / e^2$ [16].

Where: n = desired sample size, Z = confidence interval (95%) = 1.96, p = previous prevalence $p = 7\%$ [33], and e = degree of precision (0.05).

Therefore, substituting Z for 1.96, P for 0.07 and e for 0.05, then the minimum sample size will be: $n = (1.96)^2 \times 0.07 (1 - 0.07) / (0.05)^2$
 $n = 3.8416 \times 0.07 (0.93) / 0.0025 = 100$

The minimum sample size is 100 but it was adjusted to 200.

2.4 Blood sample collection

With the use of needle (22G) and 5 ml syringe, through the vein, two milliliter of blood samples were collected from pregnant women who came for Anti-Natal Care in the study area with the help of a trained nurse. After collection, the blood samples were transferred into an ethylene diamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA) container to prevent coagulation of the blood sample. Afterwards, the samples were transported to parasitology Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto (UDUSok) in a cold chain for malaria parasite screening.

2.5 Malaria parasite screening

Thick and thin blood films and Rapid Diagnostic Test kits (SD BIOLINE Malaria Ag Pf) were used to screen blood samples for the presence of malaria parasites.

2.5.1 Thin blood film

Two micro liters (2ul) of blood was placed on a pre-cleaned, labeled slide, near its frosted end. Another slide was brought at a 30-45° angle up to the drop, allowing the drop to spread along the contact line of the 2 slides. The spreader was quickly pushed toward the unfrosted end of the lower slide, making sure that the smears have a good feathered edge. This was achieved by using the correct amount of blood and spreading technique. The thin smears were allowed to dry. The smears were finally fixed by dipping them in absolute methanol [6], after which the film was flooded with giemsa stain and incubated for 15 minutes [11]., Thereafter, the stain was washed off rapidly with distilled water and allowed to dry. Two drops of immersion oil were added to the film and then viewed under the microscope at x100 objective lens for characteristics features of malaria parasite as adopted by [22].

2.5.2 *Plasmodium falciparum* Rapid Diagnostic Test Kit (RDT Kit)

All the 200 blood samples were screened using *Plasmodium falciparum* mono clonal antibody specific RDT kit to confirm the presence of the parasite (*Plasmodium falciparum*). The RDT (SD BIOLINE Malaria Ag P.f) Kit was used in accordance with the manufacture's instruction.

2.6 Statistical analysis

Fisher's Exact test was done to determine the association between the variables; *Plasmodium falciparum* parasitaemia distribution by age, level of education, trimester, parity, occupation, use of bed net, marital status and history of antimalarial drugs used by the pregnant women using InVivoStat version 4.1.0. In all the analysis, confidence level was held at 95% and $P < 0.05$ was set as level of significance.

3.0 Results

It could be seen in Table 1 that all the participants (100%) were willing to accept new drugs, sleep under bednet if supplied, and they have knowledge on the cause of malaria. 85.50% of the participants used bed net and 99.50% had received information on malaria. 92.50% of the participants reported that government has done something to control malaria, 90.80% agreed that the government supplied mosquito treated bed nets and only 17 (9.20%) agreed that government has supplied anti-malaria drugs. It is observed that, the respondents used different drugs (Fansida, chloroquine, Artemether and Emal) in treating malaria infection previously.

Of the two hundred (200) pregnant women tested for malaria using RDTthree (3) were positive for *P. falciparum*, representing 1.50% prevalence. With respect to *P. falciparum* mono clonal antibody specific RDT kit, 19 women were positive for *P. falciparum*, representing 9.50% prevalence (Table 2).

It was evident in Table 3 that the prevalence of malaria infection seemed to significantly associate ($P=0.0027$) with age (years) as pregnant women within 27-31 years of age recorded the highest prevalence (25.0%), followed by those within 22-26 years age group (16.10%), then 17-21 age group (4.35%) and pregnant women within the age group of 32-36 were found to have the least prevalence (1.79%). Increase in the prevalence of malaria was observed with increase in the age of the pregnant women from 17-31 years old. But the prevalence dropped from 32-36 years (1.79%) and no infection was detected in the older pregnant women (37-41 years old).

Although, there was no significant association ($P=1.0000$) between malaria infection and Parity condition of the pregnant women, the infection

was more prevalent among pregnant women in multigravidae (9.60%) than those with primigravidae (9.30%)(Table 3).

It could be seen from Table 3 that the distribution of malaria by trimester of the pregnant women that infection was more prevalent among pregnant women within second trimester (12.10%), followed by those within first trimester (7.40%), and pregnant women within the third trimester recorded the least prevalence of 4.10%. The occurrence of *P. falciparum* does not significantly associate ($P=0.2745$) with trimester of the pregnant women.

Although there was no significant association ($P=0.6478$) between prevalence of malaria and occupation of the pregnant women, business women recorded the highest prevalence (14.30%), followed by unemployed (10.0%), then civil servants recorded the least prevalence (7.90%) (Table 3).

Distribution of malaria by marital status of the pregnant women was shown in Table 3. Higher prevalence of malaria was recorded among widowed with 100% than married women with 9.10% prevalence. No infection was observed among pregnant women that were divorced/separated. There was no significant association ($P=0.1029$) between malaria infection and marital status of the pregnant women.

It is evident that there was no significant association ($P=0.4290$) between prevalence of malaria with history of anti-malaria drugs used by the pregnant women, malaria infection was more prevalent among those with history of using multiple drugs (Fansida, Chloroquine and Artemether) in malaria treatment with 63.20% prevalence, followed by those that used Chloroquine only and another set of multiple drugs (Fansida and Chloroquine) with 15.80% each. Participants who used Fansida recorded the least prevalence with 5.30% (Table 3).

Even though there was no significant association ($P=0.7429$) between prevalence of malaria with the use of bed net by the pregnant women (Table 13), malaria infection was found to be more prevalent among participants who claimed to be using bed net (84.20%) than those who do not use bed net with 9.50% prevalence.

It was observed (in Table 3) that malaria infection did not statistically associate ($p=1.0000$) with educational level of the pregnant women. Infection was higher among pregnant women with Non formal education (10.50%), followed by those with secondary education (10.20%), then those with tertiary education (9.30%), pregnant women with primary education recorded the least prevalence with 5.60%.

Table 1: Responses from the participating pregnant women in the study area

Variables	Frequency % (N)
Are you willing to accept new drugs?	
Yes	100 (200)
No	-
Are you willing to sleep under Bed net if supplied?	
Yes	100(200)
No	-
Do you have knowledge on the cause of malaria?	
Yes	100(200)
No	-
Use of Bed net	
Yes	85.50 (171)
No	14.50 (29)
Do you receive information on malaria?	
Yes	99.50 (199)
No	0.50 (1)
Has the government done anything to control malaria?	
Yes	92.50 (185)
No	7.50 (15)
What does the government done to control malaria?	
Supply of Mosquitoes treated bed net	90.80 (168)
Supply of Anti-malaria drugs	9.20 (17)
Other, specify	-
History of anti-malaria drugs used by the respondents in the study area	
Fansida	2.0 (4)
Chloroquine	25.50 (51)
Fansida and Chloroquine	21.0 (42)
Fansida and Emal	2.0 (4)
Fansida, Chloroquine and Artemether	49.50 (99)

Table 2: Overall Prevalence of Malaria among pregnant women using RDT kit and Microscopy

Testing Tools	Number Examined	Number Positive	Percentage Positive (%)
RDT kit	200	19	9.50
Microscopy	200	3	1.50

Table 3: Distribution of malaria by socio-demographic features of the pregnant women

Variables	Number Examined	Number Positive	Positive (%)	p-value
Age				
17-21	46	2	4.35	0.0027
22-26	62	10	16.13	
27-31	24	6	25.0	
32-36	56	1	1.79	
37-41	12	-	-	
Parity				
Primigravidae	43	4	9.30	1.0000
Multigravidae	157	15	9.6	
Trimester				
First Trimester	27	2	7.40	0.2745
Second Trimester	124	15	12.10	
Third Trimester	49	19	9.50	
Occupation				
Unemployed	130	13	10.0	0.6478
Civil servant	63	5	7.90	
Business women	7	1	14.30	
Marital status				
Married	197	18	9.10	0.1029
Divorced/Seperated	2	-	-	
Widowed	1	1	100	
Drugs				
Fansida	4	1	5.30	0.4290
Chloroquine	51	3	15.80	
Fansida and Chloroquine	42	3	15.80	
Fansida and Emal	4	-	-	
Fansida, Chloroquine and Artemether	99	12	63.20	
Use of bed net				
Yes	171	16	84.20	0.7429
No	29	3	15.80	
Level of Education				
Non Formal	19	2	10.50	1.0000
Primary	18	1	5.60	
Secondary	88	9	10.20	
Tertiary	75	7	9.30	
None	75	7	-	
Total	200	19	9.50	

4.0 Discussion

Prevalence of *P. falciparum* observed in this study (9.50%) seems to be lower compared to previous researches conducted among pregnant women attending ante-natal care in Sokoto. For instance, previous studies [26] reported 52.20% prevalence while other studies [4] reported

10.60% malaria infection prevalence also in Sokoto. This low prevalence of malaria among pregnant women in the study area may be attributed to period of the study (no rainfall), use of antimalarial drugs and the fact that the pregnant women attend ANC regularly. Earlier studies [21, 26] reported malaria prevalence to be low due to the period of the study (dry season).

In this study, significant association between *P. falciparum* parasitaemia and age of the pregnant women was observed, where pregnant women within the age range 27-31 were the highest infected and this may probably be due to the fact that the pregnant women in this category were more exposed to chloroquine which the parasite has developed resistance to as earlier reported [22]. The findings of this study are consistent with previous findings from a research conducted in a Secondary Health Care Facility in Benin City, Southern Nigeria [32] that reported significant association between malaria infection and age, where pregnant women within age group of 26-30 years (32.50%) were the highest infected. This study equally agreed with previous findings [10] conducted among pregnant women attending ANC in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital (UDUTH) Sokoto that reported significant association between malaria infection and age, where the pregnant women in age range 26-30 years (88.89%) were the highest infected. Both studies reported that there is a statistically significant association between malaria infection and age of the pregnant women, which was attributed to primigravidae state of pregnancy or lack of proper orientation regarding effects of malaria on pregnancy. Thus, making them more prone to malaria infection or exposed to mosquito bite.

Lack of association between malaria prevalence and parity of the pregnant women is an indication that all pregnant women irrespective of their parity were equally at risk of malaria infection. This may be attributed to the fact that mosquitoes are not selective on any parity group, they virtually bite and infect any human host available. This finding is inconsistent with a previous research conducted in Yemetu, Ibadan [19] that reported significant association between malaria infection and parity conditions of the pregnant women and attributed it to probably because cell-mediated immune responses to malaria antigens are more markedly suppressed in the first than in subsequent pregnancies

It could be seen that there was no association between malaria prevalence and trimester of the pregnant women. This is an indication that at any level of trimester, pregnant women were at risk of malaria infection. This may be due to the changes that occur in women's immune systems during pregnancy and the presence of a new organ (the placenta) with new places for parasites to bind,

pregnant women lose some of their immunity to malaria infection as earlier reported [5].

However, previous research [32] conducted among pregnant women attending a secondary health care facility in Benin City, Southern Nigeria reported that malaria infection was significantly associated with third trimester of the pregnant women and attributed it to the relatively small number of subjects that were involved in their study.

In this study, prevalence of malaria infection did not associate with the occupation of the pregnant women, this is an indication that pregnant women irrespective of their occupation were at risk of malaria infection. This may be attributed to the fact that mosquitoes bite and infect human host both at home, place of work or in the market. This study contradicted a previous research conducted in Zaria, Nigeria [2] where malaria infection associated with occupation (civil servants) of the pregnant women and attributed it to the fact that there were many respondents in this category whose nature of jobs exposed them to mosquito bites. It could also be as a result of the fact that majority of the civil servants in this study were males, and many studies have reported a higher prevalence of malaria in males than females. This is in agreement with previous research [14] conducted in patients with febrile complaints in Kaduna metropolis, Nigeria.

It was evident that there was no association between malaria infections with marital status of the pregnant women. This is an indication that, pregnant women without any regard to their marital status were at risk of malaria infection. This may be attributed to the fact that the malaria vector is not selective on the marital status of the pregnant women. It bites/ infect human host available. However, research conducted in Haiti [8] reported malaria infection to significantly associate with marital status of pregnant women (where pregnant women in a relationship recorded highest prevalence) and attributed it to the fact that the primary mosquito vector in Haiti (*Anopheles albimanus*) is an outdoor biter, feeding in times of dusk and dawn, when married women could be more engaged with indoor household activities rather than outdoor ones, hence less exposed to mosquito bites.

It was observed that no association between malaria infection with history of antimalarial

drugs used by the pregnant women. This is an indication that irrespective of the type of antimalarial drugs used by the pregnant women, they were at risk of malaria infection. This may be attributed to the fact that mosquitoes bite the pregnant women some time long after they had used the antimalarial drugs or probably due to the fact that the efficacy of the drugs and source could not be ascertained as many obtained the drugs from peripheral clinics, drug hawkers and chemist shops. This study contradicts a previous research conducted in Sokoto [20] that reported malaria infection to significantly associate with the use of prophylactic antimalarial drugs and attributed it to administration of intermittent preventive treatment with sulfadoxine–pyrimethamine during pregnancy (IPTp-SP), which consists of a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine given to pregnant women at routine prenatal visits, regardless of whether they were infected with malaria or not as recommended by WHO in all areas with moderate to high malaria transmission in Africa [30].

There was no association between malaria prevalence with the use of bed net by the pregnant women. This is an indication that irrespective of using bed net, the women were at risk of malaria infection. This could be attributed to the fact that mosquitoes bite the pregnant women before they entered the bed net or when they came out to ease themselves in the night. However, this study disagreed with a previous research conducted in Argungu, Kebbi State [9], where malaria infection significantly associated with the use of bed net by the pregnant women and attributed it to the fact that the nets reduced human contact with mosquitoes, thus leading to a significant reduction in the incidence of malaria, associated morbidity and mortality as well as in the adverse effects during pregnancy in areas of intense malaria transmission as earlier reported [23].

In this study, it was evident that there was no association between prevalence of malaria with level of education of the pregnant women. This is an indication that without regard to the level of education of the pregnant women, they were at risk of malaria infection. This may be attributed to the fact that some of the pregnant women were not aware of the preventive measures or there was negligence among those who were already aware. However, this finding is inconsistent with

previous research conducted in Argungu, Kebbi State by [9], who reported that malaria infection significantly associated with the level of education of the pregnant women and attributed it to the role education could have on the overall success of malaria control programs in the region and recommended that government policies be geared towards improving citizens' education status in order to reduce the burden of the disease in the country, especially among the most vulnerable population

5.0 Conclusion

This study has revealed high prevalence of malaria infection among pregnant women attending ante natal care in the study area. It was observed from this study that pregnant women within the age group 27-31 years, women that are multigravidae, women in second trimester, business women, those with no formal education and women with previous history of using chloroquine, fansida and artemether were the highest infected.

6.0 Recommendations

1. Malaria control program should be targeted to women in age group 27-31 years, those in second trimester, women that are multigravidae, business women and those with no formal education.
2. Since the participants were willing to accept new drugs if supplied, pharmaceutical industries should develop drugs that will substitute chloroquine, Mefloquine, Halofantrine, and Lumefantrine whose continuous use in malaria treatment posed continuous spread of the mutant genes as the parasite (*P. falciparum*) has developed resistance against the drugs.
3. Pregnant women should be sleeping under mosquito bed net and be attending ante-natal care regularly.
4. There is the need for continuous awareness on the cause, effects, prevention and medication of malaria infection, particularly among pregnant women by the government and agencies in charge to curb the lingering effects of malaria infection and spread of the mutant genes in the State.

7.0 Conflict of Interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

8.0 References

- 2017;22(8):1030-1036.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/tmi.12909>.
- [1] Apinjoh TO, Anchang-Kimbi JK, Mugri RN, Tangoh DA, Nyingchu RV, Chi HF. The effect of insecticide treated nets (ITNs) on *Plasmodium falciparum* infection in rural and semi-urban communities in the south west region of Cameroon. PLoS ONE, 2015;10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0116300>.
- [2] Benjamin GY, Kanai ET, Moses BE, Aluwong GS. Demographic factors associated with Malaria Prevalence in Zaria, Kaduna, Nigeria. Bayero Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences, 2006;10(1):116–119.
- [3] Bhatt S, Weiss DJ, Cameron E, Bisanzio D, Mappin B, Dalrymple U. The effect of malaria control on *Plasmodium falciparum* in Africa between 2000 and 2015. European pub, 2015;8(526):207-211. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature15535>.
- [4] Buhari HA, Erhabor O, Momodu I. *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria among pregnant women attending Ante-Natal Clinic in Sokoto, north western, Nigeria. Sokoto Journal of Medical Laboratory Science. 2016;(1):187–193
- [5] CDC. Intermittent preventive treatment of malaria for pregnant women (IPTp). Centre for Disease Control and Prevention 2018 malaria report. 2018; https://www.cdc.gov/malaria/malaria_worldwide/reduction/iptp.html.
- [6] CDC. DPDx-Laboratory Identification of parasites of public health concern. Centre for Disease Control and Prevention. CDC - DPDx - Diagnostic procedures – Blood Specimens.2020; <https://www.cdc.gov/specimenproc>
- [7] C-GIDD. Canback Global Income Distribution Database Location of Sokoto State, Nigeria. 2008; 1-2pp.
- [8] Elbadry MA, Massimiliano S, Tagliamonte C, Raccurt P, Jean F, Lemoine AE. Submicroscopic malaria infections in pregnant women from six departments in Haiti. Tropical Medicine and International Health. 2017;22(8):1030-1036.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/tmi.12909>.
- [9] Fana SA, Bunza MD, Anka SA, Imam AU, Nataala SU. Prevalence and risk factors associated with malaria infection among pregnant women in a semi-urban community of north-western Nigeria. Infectious Diseases Poverty. 2015;4(24),123-130. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40249-015-0054-0>.
- [10] Faruku N, Magaji UF, Bunza NM, Bello M. Parity and malaria parasitaemia among pregnant women attending ANC, UDUTH Sokoto. International Journal of Medical and Health Research. 2016;2(9), 61-64.
- [11] Giemsa, G., 1902. Technique for thick blood film. Zbl. Bakt. Ref.
- [12] Gomes PS, Bhardwaj J, Rivera-Correa J, Freire-De-Lima CG, Morrot A. [Immune Escape Strategies of Malaria Parasites](#)". Frontiers in Microbiology. 2016; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmicb.2016.01617>.
- [13] Griffin JT, Ferguson NM, Ghani AC. Estimates of the changing age-burden of *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria disease in sub-Saharan Africa. Nat Commun. 2014;5:3136. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms4136>.
- [14] Idoko MO, Ado S, Umoh V. Prevalence of dengue virus and malaria in patients with febrile complaints in Kaduna metropolis, Nigeria, British Research Journal 2015;8(1), 343-347.
- [15] Lema SY, Suleiman J, Rabi'atu MS, A'isha U, Yakubu MS. Prevalence of *Trichomonas vaginalis* among pregnant women attending antenatal care (ANC), maryam abacha women and children hospital, Sokoto, Nigeria. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research. 2019;6(3), 52-56.
- [16] Lwanga SK, Lemeshow S, WHO. Sample size determination in health studies: a practical manual / Lwanga SK. and Lemeshow S. World Health Organization. 1991; <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/40062>.

- [17] Maina AT, Auta IK, Nock IH. Prevalence of *Plasmodium falciparum* in participants at selected hospitals, Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Parasitology*. 2017;38(2).
- [18] Molina-Cruz A, Canepa GE, Kamath N, Pavlovic NV, Mu J, Ramphul UN. *Plasmodium* evasion of mosquito immunity and global malaria transmission: the lock-and-key theory. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*. 2015;8(49), 78-83. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1520426112.
- [19] Okorofor UP, Isegbe EI, Ikokoh MO, Ogbu UM. Malaria parasitaemia among pregnant women attending antenatals in a Nigerian specialists hospital. *International Journal of Innovative Healthcare Research*. 2020;8(3), 1-4
- [20] Osaro E, Abdullahi A, Tosan E. Risk factors associated with malaria infection among pregnant women of African descent in specialist hospital Sokoto, Nigeria. *Obstetric Gynecology International Journal*. 2019;10(4), 274-280.
- [21] Patricia N, Okorie KO, Popoola K, Olayemi M, Awobifa K, Ibrahim T. Species composition and temporal distribution of mosquito population in Ibadan, southwest Nigeria. *Journal of Entomology and Zoology studies*. 2014;2(4), 164-169.
- [22] Simon-Oke IA, Obimakinde ET, Afolabi OJ. Prevalence and distribution of malaria, Pfcrt and Pfmdr 1 genes in patients attending FUT Health Centre, Akure, Nigeria. *Beni-Suef University Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*. 2018;7 (pp 98–103).
- [23] TerKuile FO, Terlouw DJ, Philips-Howard PA, Hawley WA, Friedman JF, Kariuki SK. Reduction of malaria during pregnancy by permethrin-treated bed nets in an area of intense perennial malaria transmission in western Kenya. *American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*. 2003;64(2), 50–60.
- [24] Tobias O A, Amed O, Vincent PK, Titanji A, Alfred A. Genetic diversity and drug resistance surveillance of *Plasmodium falciparum* for malaria elimination. *Malaria Journal*. 2019;18(p 217).
- [25] Trape JF, Tall A, Diagne N, Ndiath O, Ly AB, Faye J, Raoult D. Malaria morbidity and pyrethroid resistance after the introduction of insecticide-treated bed nets and artemisinin-based combination therapies: a longitudinal study. *Lancet Infectious Diseases*. 2011;11(12), 925-932. doi: 10.1016/S1473-3099(11)70194-3.
- [26] Udomah FP, Isaac IZ, Lukman I, Nwobodo D, Erhabor O, Abdulrahman Y. *Plasmodium* Parasitaemia among pregnant women attending antenatal clinic in Sokoto, north western Nigeria. *Journal of Nursing Science*. 2015;1(1), 9-14.
- [27] Watson OJ, Slater HC, Verity R, Parr JB, Mwandagalirwa MK, Tshefu A. Modelling the drivers of the spread of *Plasmodium falciparum* *hrp2* gene deletions in sub-Saharan Africa. *Elife*. 2017;doi:10.7554/eLife.25008.
- [28] WHO Global Malaria Program. The role of mass drug administration, mass screening and treatment, and focal screening and treatment for malaria: recommendations. Geneva: World Health Organization. 2015.
- [29] WHO. World Malaria report 2016. World Health Organization. 2016; <https://www.who.int/malaria/publications/world-malaria-report-2016/report/en/>
- [30] WHO. [World malaria report 2018](#). World Health Organization. Retrieved 2 December 2018. 2018; <https://www.who.int/malaria/publications/world-malaria-report-2018/en/>.
- [31] WHO. [World Malaria Report 2019](#). Switzerland: World Health Organization. 2019; pp. 4–10. [ISBN 978-92-4-156572-1](#).
- [32] Wogu MD, Obasohan HO. Malaria Parasitaemia and Anaemia among Pregnant Women Attending a Secondary Health Care Facility in Benin City, Southern Nigeria. *American-Eurasian Journal of Scientific Research*. 2014;9(4), 76-81.
- [33] Ekpereonne E, Effa E, Udoh E, Oduwole O, Chibuzor M, Oyo-Ita A. [Utilization of intermittent preventive treatment for malaria among pregnant women attending antenatal](#)

[clinics in health facilities of Cross River State, Nigeria.](#) 2017;19(4),29-35. doi: 10.2147/RRTM.S47677.

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